

CREEP BEHAVIOR OF A SiC_f/Ti-1100 COMPOSITE AT 540°C

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ABSTRACT

A SiC_f/Ti-1100 [0]₈ composite was creep tested at 540°C; stress was applied parallel to the fiber axis. Tests were performed at stresses ranging from 950 MPa to 730 MPa. All tests demonstrated shorter lives than predicted by the McLean/Curtin creep model. This model assumes the matrix relaxes according to a generalized power-law equation. However, fractography of these tests revealed regions of intergranular matrix cracking that dominated creep behavior of the composite at this temperature. The possibility exists of eliminating this matrix cracking behavior by altering the microstructure through heat-treatment.

INTRODUCTION

For the past several years, tremendous efforts have been expended to understand and use continuously-reinforced titanium matrix composites (TMCs). The aerospace community, in particular, has had a great deal of interest in the application of TMCs in both airframe and turbine engine components. TMC is considered to be a critical materials' technology to enable the next leap forward in turbine engine science. Many of the engine applications of the conventional titanium-alloy matrix composites require the material to perform at moderately high temperatures, and creep is one of the critical high temperature behaviors to understand. Models of creep behavior have been proposed, but their usefulness in predicting the behavior of TMCs has not been established.

The purpose of this work was to measure the creep performance of The SiC_f/Ti-1100 [0]₈ composite loaded parallel to the fiber axis at 540°C. The matrix alloy, Ti-1100, was designed for use at temperatures as high as 593°C, and it was hoped that the improved elevated temperature properties that this alloy demonstrated in monolithic form would translate to improved creep resistance in the composite. Recent advances in modeling of the creep of continuously-reinforced metals [1] have resulted in the capability to predict the onset of tertiary creep and fracture. In the present study this new model is employed to predict the creep-rupture life of SiC_f/Ti-1100 composite at 540°C.

MATERIAL

THE MATRIX

The chemistry of Ti-1100 is (in weight percent) 6.0 Al, 2.8 Sn, 4 Zr, 0.4 Mo, 0.45 Si, 0.07 O₂, and the balance titanium. It is one of several near-alpha, alpha-beta alloys similar to Ti-6242S. The high silicon content of Ti-1100 is thought to improve the high-temperature (593°C) tensile

strength and the creep resistance of the alloy. The optimum processing procedures and microstructure/property relationships of this alloy have been discussed elsewhere [2, 3].

THE FIBER

The SiC fiber used in this study was manufactured by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) of SiC fibers on to a carbon monofilament. The CVD process is also employed to produce a protective carbonaceous coating on the fiber surface. The fiber chemistry and structure have been analyzed by several authors [4-6].

THE COMPOSITE

The composite was fabricated by a process known as 'foil-fiber-foil' (FFF) which describes the alternating layers of matrix foil and fiber mat which are stacked and consolidated by hot isostatic pressing (HIPing). The SiC_f/Ti-1100 [0]₈ composite was manufactured in this manner from Ti-1100 foil and a woven mat of SiC fiber. The resulting composite panels had an average volume fraction of fiber of 0.416. A typical composite cross-section is shown in Figure 1a, and the matrix microstructure is illustrated in Figure 1b. The mean α -phase grain diameter in the matrix is 8.8 μm with a small amount of intergranular β -phase. The large globular precipitates are titanium, zirconium silicides. It is likely that the very fine precipitates (50 - 100 nm in diameter) are also Ti-silicides, but their small diameter precluded their identification.

a

b

Figure 1. A typical composite cross-section (a) and the Ti-1100 matrix microstructure (b).

THE MODEL

Of the models of creep in continuous fiber composites that have been proposed, the model developed by McLean [7] is the most widely used and accepted. The major limitation of the McLean model is that it is incapable of predicting creep-rupture. Du and McMeeking [1] incorporate the concepts of global load redistribution and reloading of broken fibers within a composite developed by Curtin [8] to modify the McLean creep model. The resulting McLean/Curtin model describes the behavior of a composite in which fibers may fail over a range of composite strain during a creep test. The stress distribution in the creep specimen changes due to both matrix relaxation and fiber fracture. The McLean/Curtin model forecasts that when sufficient fiber fracture has occurred to increase stress in the matrix, the creep strain rate will increase and tertiary creep and composite fracture ensue.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

For this study, the strength distribution of fibers extracted from the Ti-1100 matrix was measured, and the power-law behavior of the matrix was analyzed [9]. From these properties, the creep behavior of the composite was predicted using the McLean/Curtin model.

After fabrication, the composite panel was sectioned, and four creep specimens were machined with a reduced gage. Each specimen was prepared by polishing the reduced section to remove any material contaminated by the consolidation process. The specimens were then cleaned with acetone to remove any dirt and oil. Three creep tests were conducted in a horizontally-oriented, hydraulic load frame. The specimens were gripped by water-cooled, pneumatic wedge grips. The gage was heated using a bank of four quartz bulbs above and below the specimen. Temperature in the gage was controlled by four thermocouples tack-welded to the face of the specimen. Strain was monitored using an extensometer with quartz knife-edges held against the specimen at a gage length of about 12.5 mm. Specimens were placed in the test frame and heated to a temperature of 540°C and held for 10-20 minutes before loading. Tests were performed under load control. Two specimens were tested at a stress of 950 MPa and one at 730 MPa. The specimen tested at 805 MPa was loaded vertically in a dead-load frame with heated grips; other test procedures were similar to those previously described.

After testing, the fracture surface of each specimen was removed, cleaned, and examined on the SEM. Specimen 94-E04 was unloaded prior to failure, and was examined by ultrasonic, non-destructive evaluation (NDE) techniques to identify any fiber damage or matrix cracking that might have been present. Following NDE the specimen was failed in tension at 540°C.

RESULTS

The McLean/Curtin model predicted that at stresses of 950 MPa and lower, creep-rupture would not occur in less than 1000 hours at 540°C. Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the creep strain versus time behavior of those specimens tested at 950 MPa and 805 MPa, respectively. Specimens 94-E05 and 94-E06 were tested at 950 MPa. The maximum creep strain reached was 0.077% and the stress-rupture life was 7.2 hours for 94-E05; the maximum creep strain for 94-E06 was 0.096% with a rupture life of 7.0 hours. Specimen 94-512, tested at 805 MPa, reached a maximum creep strain of 0.21% in 30.2 hours. The fourth creep test on specimen 94-E04 was loaded to a constant stress of 730 MPa, continued for 145 hours, and unloaded without failure. The total strain versus time is plotted in Figure 4; the maximum creep strain reached was 0.031%. NDE inspection revealed significant attenuation in the signal energy at the shoulder and ends of the reduced gage which is generally indicative of matrix cracks. The subsequent tensile test of 94-E04 at 540°C resulted in failure at a maximum stress of 670 MPa within the damaged region identified by NDE.

The fracture surfaces of specimens 94-E05, E06, 512, and E04 are shown in Figures 5a,b,c, and d, respectively. All except 94-E04 showed evidence of two different fracture morphologies. In the area of the fracture surface near the machined edges of the gage of 94-E05, E06, and 512, the matrix fracture was intergranular (Figure 6a) and there was little fiber pullout. In the center of the cross-sections of these fracture surfaces, the matrix fracture was highly ductile (Figure 6b), and substantially more fiber pull-out was evident. The total area of intergranular fracture

Figure 2. Creep strain versus time for specimens 94-E05 and -E06, tested at 950 MPa.

Figure 3. Creep strain versus time for specimen 94-512, tested at 805 MPa.

Figure 4. Creep strain versus time for specimen 94-E04, tested at 730 MPa.

in specimens 94-E05 and E06 was 33% and 24%, respectively. Specimen 94-512 showed intergranular matrix cracking over 59% of its fracture surface. The intergranular fracture area gives the appearance of one or more cracks growing inward from the machined edges in these specimens. Multiple levels of fracture were also in evidence on specimen 94-512, which suggests multiple matrix cracks grew on different planes and linked at failure. The tensile fracture surface of specimen 94-E04 had multiple planes, all of which demonstrate completely intergranular matrix fracture. Several cracks were also present away from the actual fracture surface, and these also appeared to be intergranular.

Figure 5. Fracture surfaces of specimens 95-E05 (a), 95-E06 (b), 95-512 (c), and 95-E04 (d).

Figure 6. Typical areas of intergranular matrix fracture (a) and ductile matrix fracture (b).

DISCUSSION

The extremely short (compared to model predictions) creep lives observed experimentally in this composite system at 540°C were due to the accumulation of significant matrix damage in the form of intergranular cracks. In specimens 94-E05, E06, and 512 there were two cracks that appeared to propagate from the specimen edges (Figures 3a, b, and c). NDE of specimen 94-E04 indicated a significant amount of matrix damage, and the subsequent tensile fracture was completely intergranular. Conversely, little evidence of fiber fracture during the creep tests was observed.

The specific mechanism of intergranular matrix cracking was not discerned in this investigation. It is unlikely that the cracking is caused by rapid grain boundary cavitation associated with creep crack growth. Although creep crack growth has been observed in Ti-6242 [10], no evidence of cavity formation at the grain boundaries was found in the Ti-1100 matrix (Figure 7). It is probable that environmental factors played a role in accelerating the cracking process. Such accelerated crack growth has been linked to environmental effects in certain nickel-based alloys [11], and similar intergranular fracture has also been observed in low-cycle fatigue of Ti-1100 matrix composite in air at 538°C [12]. The shape of the intergranular regions observed on the fracture surfaces of specimens 94-E05, E06, and 512 is evidence that these cracks initiated at the machined surface of the gage and grew toward the specimen center; no internally-initiated cracks were observed.

Because the McLean/Curtin model considers only fiber damage, while the matrix is assumed to undergo stress-relaxation, the model did not accurately predict the creep life of the SCS-6/Ti-1100 composite at 540°C. No adjustment of the constituent parameters input to the model significantly altered its prediction of creep-rupture life. Nor did the inclusion of elastic residual stresses in the model initial conditions have the desired effect. The limitation of this model lay in its simplistic approach to matrix deformation and inability to incorporate time-dependent matrix damage. To model the observed creep behavior, the rate of intergranular crack growth and the effect of matrix cracking on bridging fiber strength must be quantified. However, the presence of multiple crack initiations would make this a difficult feat.

One approach to alleviating the problem of modeling matrix damage accumulation is to identify a heat-treatment process by which the microstructure of the matrix may be significantly altered to prevent matrix crack growth. Intergranular cracking has not been observed in monolithic Ti-1100 with a Widmanstätten microstructure [13], and previous efforts

[9, 14] have shown that a substantial thermal exposure of the composite is required to significantly degrade the fiber strength; so, there may be sufficient latitude in processing to develop a post-consolidation heat-treatment to change the matrix structure from fine, equiaxed α -phase grains with silicide precipitates to one of transformed β -phase laths with fewer silicides without destroying fiber properties. Figure 8 shows an example of a modified matrix microstructure that resulted from a composite heat-treatment at 1100°C for 30 minutes; it appears that the silicides have dissolved and that selected regions have transformed to a lath structure.

Figure 7. High magnification view of the intergranular fracture surface which shows no evidence of cavitation.

Figure 8. A backscattered electron image of SiC_f/Ti-1100 microstructure following a heat-treatment at 1100°C for 30 minutes.

CONCLUSIONS

1. SiC_f/T-1100 composite demonstrated abbreviated creep life at 540°C due to the rapid development of intergranular cracks in the matrix.
2. Intergranular matrix cracks appear to initiate at the machined edges of the composite specimens and grow by an environmentally-assisted mechanism.
3. The McLean/Curtin model of creep in unidirectionally-reinforced composites could not accurately predict the rupture life of the composite at 540°C. The model cannot accommodate the matrix cracks that lead composite failure.
4. Heat-treatment of the composite above the β -transus temperature to alter this microstructure could potentially improve the crack resistance of the matrix and extend the creep life of the composite without significantly damaging the fibers or interface.

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